

Katumuwa Stele from Sam'al

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The Katumuwa Stele is a monumental funerary effigy from the eighth century BCE that was commissioned by a royal official named Katumuwa (or possibly Kuttamuwa) from the Aramean kingdom of Sam'al (also called Ya'diya). It was discovered in July of 2008 during the Oriental Institute's Neubeauer Expedition in Zincirli, Turkey and subsequently published the following year (Pardee 2009 [editio princeps]). Zincirli (ancient Sam'al/Ya'diya), a 40-hectare ruin mound (Turkish höyük, Arabic tell), served as the capital city of the Iron Age kingdom of Sam'al (fl. 900-713 BCE) and afterward as a province of the Neo-Assyrian empire. The large basalt stele was discovered in Building A/II of Complex A in the northern lower town of the site, namely Katumuwa's mortuary chapel, although it probably was originally a domestic residence. It's possible that the adjacent room, called by the excavators Building A/III, was a small neighborhood temple to one of the gods mentioned in the inscription, which itself comports with other evidence for a royal mortuary cult at Sam'al. In fact, veneration of the spirits of the royal and ancestral dead, especially feasts for the dead, is widely known from ancient Mesopotamia and the Levant (see e.g. Lewis 2014). The Katumuwa Stele, however, is unique in that it's the best preserved mortuary stele that combines both a banquet scene as well as an inscription from the first-person perspective of the beneficiary. The introduction states: "I am Katumuwa, servant of Panamuwa, who commissioned for myself (this) stele while still living. I placed it in my eternal chamber and established a feast (at) this chamber" (Pardee 2014). The inscription proceeds to outline the instructions for the feast wherein a bull and five rams are sacrificed for the following five deities as well as Katumuwa's post-mortem "essence" (נַפְשׁוֹ, often translated "soul") that is in the stele itself: Hadad-Qarpatalli (one bull), NGD/R-ŞWD/RN (one ram), Šamš (one ram), Hadad-of-the-Vineyards (one ram), Kubaba (one ram), and Katumuwa (one ram). The second half of the inscription then provides further instructions for whomever comes into possession of the chamber, namely that he should perform the yearly offering "from the best (produce) of this vineyard" in addition to the slaughter prescribed above. The stele's banquet scene also provides a source of valuable information for understanding how Katumuwa feasts in the afterlife. Katumuwa is depicted as sitting in a chair with his feet resting on a footstool. A table sits in front of him arrayed with food, specifically bread, meat (a duck?), and a container with some sort of spices or aromatics. In his hands are a drinking bowl (right) and a conifer cone on a branch (left). Finally, the winged sun-disk tops the stele representing the protection of Šamš. Importantly, this mortuary banquet scene shares a number of iconographic parallels with similar banquet scenes from Zincirli and elsewhere in Syro-Hittite art, e.g. the Aramaic-inscribed Neirab Stele of the priest Si-Gabbar. As such, the Katumuwa Stele stands as a testament to the rich cultural heritage of the ancient kingdom of Sam'al and provides an important window into the religious beliefs and cultic practices of its inhabitants.

Date Range: 900 BCE - 700 BCE

Region: Yādiya/Sam'al

Region tags: Asia Minor, Levant

The kingdom of Yādiya was based at the city of Sam'al (Zincirli Höyük), but it also included a necropolis at Gercin and perhaps more of the surrounding area.

Status of Readership:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Dennis Pardee. “A New Aramaic Inscription from Zincirli.” *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 356 (2009): 51-71.
- Source 2: Virginia Rimmer Herrmann and J. David Schloen, eds. *In Remembrance of Me: Feasting with the Dead in the Ancient Middle East*. Chicago: The Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago, 2014.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://isac.uchicago.edu/museum-exhibits/special-exhibits/remembrance-me-feasting-dead-ancient-middle-east>OLD#:~:text=The%20exhibit%20In%20Remembrance%20of,%2C%20Egypt%2C%20and%20the%20Levant.
- Source 1 Description: Museum Exhibit related to Katumuwa at the Institute for the Study of Ancient Cultures
- Source 2 URL: <https://isac.uchicago.edu/research/publications/oimp/oimp-37-remembrance-me-feasting-dead-ancient-middle-east>
- Source 2 Description: Publications related to Katumuwa at the Institute for the Study of Ancient Cultures
- Source 3 URL: <https://isac-idb.uchicago.edu/id/54146c2c-b8b7-49c5-b2fd-b84e8794c4a6>
- Source 3 Description: Museum Item of Katumuwa at the Institute for the Study of Ancient Cultures

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Incised or Inscribed

Method of inscription

- Chisel
- Other [specify]: The inscription and banquet scene are sculpted in raised relief, a common practice in Syro-Hittite art.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Stone

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– Yes

Notes: It seems likely that Building A/II was a mortuary chapel while the adjacent room, Building A/III, was a neighborhood temple.

↳ Shrine

– Yes

Notes: Scholars refer to Building A/II as Katumuwa's "mortuary chapel" or "local mortuary shrine". The inscription makes reference to Katumuwa's "essence" (or "soul") which is in the stele itself. While still alive, Katumuwa "established a feast" (Aram. *ḥgg) which possibly suggests that Katumuwa's chapel, or shrine, was a local pilgrimage destination.

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church
– No

↳ Mosque
– No

↳ Synagogue
– No

↳ Triumphal Arch
– No

↳ Monument
– Yes

Notes: The text and banquet scene are inscribed on the stele which itself functions as the effigy. It bears Katumuwa's image and is presumably inhabited by his post-mortem "essence" (or soul), at least during the time of the annual sacrificial feasts.

↳ Mass Gathering Point
– Field doesn't know

Notes: Based on the size of the sacrifices, i.e. one bull and five rams, it appears probable that the chapel served as a somewhat sizable gathering point for a mix of individuals, including members of the royal or social elite, religious specialists, family, and/or friends who partook in the feast(s).

↳ Cave(s)
– No

↳ Hilltops
– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries
– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines
– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

Library/archive

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: The iconography, including the image of Katumuwa feasting at a banquet, is included with the inscription on the stele, but the text is not stored in a location which includes separate iconography or images.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Katumuwa was a servant of the king, Panamuwa, so it seems possible that the production of the text, mortuary shrine, and/or sacrificial feast(s) were funded or subsidized, either initially or perpetually, by the polity. More likely, however, is that Katumuwa and/or his family funded the production of the text and the operation of his mortuary cult. Lines 6-10a also suggests this conclusion: "Henceforth, whoever of my sons or of the sons of anybody (else) should come into possession of this chamber, let him take from the best (produce) of this vine(yard) (as) a (presentation?)-offering year by year."

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text makes mention of a yearly sacrifice/offering and what seems to be a ritual practice wherein the prescribed sacrifice is performed "on my [Katumuwa's] 'soul'" (Aram. bnbšy; line 5), however the practice is unclear. Does the "soul" (or essence) refer to Katumuwa's post-mortem existence within the stele or the image inscribed upon it? More specifically, does performing the sacrifice "on the soul" allude to an elusive practice of smearing the blood of the sacrifice on Katumuwa's image? The role of the stele in a ritual practice seems possible but the details remain unclear.

Is there material significance to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

↳ Calligraphy?

– No

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

Notes: The illustration which accompanies the text is a banquet scene which shows Katumuwa enjoying a feast.

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

Notes: The text includes a list of sacrifices for a set of deities as well as Katumuwa himself.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Field doesn't know

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: The distinction is implied.

Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: The distinction is implied by the existence of Katumuwa's being/essence after death.

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The only indication is that Katumuwa's soul/essence is located in/on the stele. This could imply that the stele is merely an earthly proxy for Katumuwa's post-mortem existence, the location of which otherwise remains unknown.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: While the temporality of the afterlife is not specified within the text, there is indication of a yearly sacrifice/offering performed by Katumuwa's mortuary cult, specifically his son or whoever else comes to possess the chamber and its accompanying vineyard.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Notes: A few of the lexical items in the text are debated, such as the word for "(mortuary)

chamber" itself, but the text does not specify the language of the afterlife in significant detail.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Notes: There are no special treatments for Katumuwa's physical corpse. There is, however, special treatment for Katumuwa's soul/essence which is somehow associated with the stele itself.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The status of the cultic actions seem to fit the description of veneration better than "worship".

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– Field doesn't know

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– Field doesn't know

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the deceased human is venerated, his deification status is unclear.

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– Field doesn't know

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Several deities are present in a list of sacrificial offerings but none are set apart as a supreme high-god.

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In the traditional sense, the human spirit is not "seen". However, Katumuwa's "soul/essence" (נפש) has been interpreted as referring to the image of him in the banquet scene of the stele.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text is not explicit, but Aramaean religion can be reconstructed as such that non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world. In the Katumuwa Stele, it seems almost certain that the gods mentioned would have knowledge of the sacrifices presented to them by the mortuary cult.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: While it's not explicitly mentioned in the text, it seems likely that the gods were understood as having causal efficacy in the world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Notes: While it's not explicitly mentioned in the text, it seems likely that the gods were understood as having causal efficacy in the world.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text does not explicitly state that the supernatural beings possess hunger, but the assumption is warranted on the basis that the mortuary cult provides sacrifices to them and Katumuwa.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text attests to a worship of multiple deities and perhaps a hierarchy among them, since Hadad-Qarpatalli is allotted an entire bull while the other deities, such as Šamš and Kubaba, are offered a ram.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The ontological character of Katumuwa's post-mortem "essence" is unclear, but associating him as (semi-)divine is not unwarranted. His name appears in a list among the other deities, and he is clearly the object of cult and sacrificial offerings.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The relationship between Katumuwa's post-mortem "essence" and the stele itself remains unclear as to whether his so-called "soul" (נפש) resides in (or "on") the stele (Aram. בנצב) or if the stele is merely a proxy substitute.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires sacrifice of animals in a feast.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires the cultic officiants to spend time making sacrifices annually on behalf of Katumuwa.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It seems likely that Katumuwa is establishing an annual feast, although the number of participants involved in the associated ritual(s) is unknown.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text makes reference to Katumuwa's "son" who will in the future come into possession of the chamber and vineyard. The reference to the "son" is probably literal but could in theory be understood as fictive.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The sacrifices total one bull and five rams.

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: Hadad-Qarpatalli (one bull), NGD/R-ṢWD/RN (one ram), Šamš (one ram), Hadad-of-the-Vineyards (one ram), Kubaba (one ram), and Katumuwa (one ram)

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In addition to the animal sacrifices, the text makes mention of some sort of "(presentation-)offering" (אֶשֶׁת), perhaps taken "from the best (produce) of this vineyard."

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Notes: Mention is not made of the physical maintenance of the mortuary chapel, except that the prescribed feast should occur yearly. The place's regular maintenance may be deduced from the reference to the "best (produce) of this vineyard".

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A city-state

Notes: Scholars mostly refer to the ancient "kingdom" of Sam'al wherein Sam'al (modern Zincirli) is the capital. After 713 BCE, it became a province of the Neo-Assyrian empire.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The sacrifice of animals for the gods and Katumuwa implies food production. It seems likely that the food would not have been wasted and that the food was used in an accompanying feast for some combination of the officiants of the mortuary cult, family members, and/or the social elite.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Katumuwa Stele from Sam'al, Younger, Jr., K. Lawson. "The Ördekburnu and Katumuwa Stelae: Some Reflections on Two Grabdenkmäler". *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 384 (2020): 1-19.

Reference: Katumuwa Stele from Sam'al, Younger, Jr., K. Lawson. "Two Epigraphic Notes on the New Katumuwa Inscription from Zincirli". *Maarav* 16, no. 2 (2009): 159-79.

Reference: Katumuwa Stele from Sam'al, Pardee, Dennis. "A New Aramaic Inscription from Zincirli". *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 356 (2009): 51-71.

Reference: Katumuwa Stele from Sam'al, Sanders, Seth L.. "The Appetites of the Dead: West Semitic Linguistic and Ritual Aspects of the Katumuwa Stele". *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental*

Research 369 (2013): 35-55.

Reference: Katumuwa Stele from Sam'al, Herrmann, Virginia Rimmer, and J. David Schloen, eds.. In *Remembrance of Me: Feasting with the Dead in the Ancient Middle East*. Edited by Virginia Rimmer Herrmann and J. David Schloen. Chicago: The Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago, 2014.